

SlideRule Software as a model for Open Source Science for Earth System Observatory Mission Science Data Processing

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SlideRule is a software framework for on demand science data processing on Cloud computing infrastructure that involves several innovative open-source software packages working in concert. SlideRule development has been guided by a fundamental change in the way Earth science data is distributed by institutions and interacted with by data users. Historically, institutions *pre-generate datasets* which are archived and made available via data centers. Data users download parts of those datasets from the data centers and perform local processing and analysis. SlideRule models an alternative approach that is centered around *services*. Institutions make science data available via web services, and data users integrate those web services directly into their existing data analysis systems. This new approach is enabled by co-locating low-level instrument data with scalable compute resources, and permits efficient generation of *both* global standard products and custom user-defined derived datasets.

The development of SlideRule was led by the University of Washington in collaboration with NASA Goddard and has been funded by NASA's ICESat-2 mission¹. SlideRule is designed to be extensible in anticipation of upcoming Earth System Observatory (ESO) Missions, and takes advantage of ICESat-2 being one of the first NASA missions to have archival data products hosted in commercial cloud object storage (AWS S3 in us-west-2). The University of Washington's deployment of SlideRule runs in AWS us-west-2 and consists of a single autoscaling cluster of EC2 instances that have access to NASA's Cumulus datasets in S3, and NASA's Common Metadata Repository (CMR). Users can access the system via an HTTP API, as well as a Python client.

Figure 1: SlideRule System Architecture

In this document we'll describe the basic architecture of SlideRule, and how its design and technical components are relevant to future ESO data processing architectures. We also document our approach to open source software development and how that fits into NASA's push for Open Science. Lastly, we will talk about key technologies and features of SlideRule that are necessary for new science data processing systems.

¹ For more information, see <http://icesat2sliderule.org>

1. Data Processing System Architecture

SlideRule is a mature server-side framework written in *Python / C++ / Lua* that provides REST APIs (i.e. web services) for on demand science data processing. SlideRule can be used by researchers and other data systems for low-latency access to customized data products that are generated using processing parameters supplied at the time of the request. SlideRule has been actively developed over the last two years, and is regularly used to generate gridded elevation sets for regions all over the world. The driving principles behind SlideRule's design are: all infrastructure is deployed from code, all components of the deployment are ephemeral, processing requests are stateless, and computation should occur as close to the data as possible.

Infrastructure as Code

The SlideRule development team uses *Terraform* for provisioning all resources in AWS. The entire system is recreated from scratch for every deployment, and multiple deployments can exist next to each other while remaining completely independent and unaware of the others. Managing the infrastructure this way protects against configuration drift, and provides a template for migrating the system to other Cloud providers.

Ephemeral Components

The base unit of deployment for SlideRule is a *provisioned cluster*, which consists of an AWS Autoscaling Group that runs the SlideRule processing nodes and a stand-alone EC2 instance that runs SlideRule's monitoring and service discovery system. All components in SlideRule are run inside *Docker* containers that register their services for a fixed amount of time, making security and feature updates easier to deploy, and also allowing SlideRule to be cost-effective. When SlideRule is not in use, its costs can scale down to a single EC2 instance and an empty S3 bucket used for storing configuration. When processing demand requires it, the number of processing nodes can scale up to thousands to handle incoming requests.

Stateless Requests

Each processing request to a SlideRule processing node stands on its own and has no knowledge of any other processing request. Parallelization in SlideRule is coordinated by the client. This gives data users full visibility into the compute resources available and gives them flexibility in how they use those resources. The development team provides a Python client that implements parallelization with default retries and backoff behavior. Because SlideRule is coordinated through HTTP requests, clients in other open source programming languages such as R and Julia are straightforward.

Compute Next to Data

SlideRule is designed to run next the data - meaning it assumes that access to source datasets are efficient, and data transfers to users are inefficient. For this reason, it maximizes the bandwidth available for reading source data, while minimizing response traffic back to users.

2. Open Science

SlideRule strives to be a part of the open science movement through permissive licensing, open development, extensive user documentation, and public outreach. With publicly-accessible endpoints, researchers can share reproducible analysis scripts without needing to worry about local computational resources or data management; this is hugely advantageous for collaborative investigations.

Open Source and Openly Developed

All of the software for SlideRule is open source under the permissive **BSD 3-clause license** and developed in the open on **GitHub**². Users are encouraged to browse the code, fork the repositories and submit pull requests, open issues, and post discussion topics. Being open source has allowed us to collaborate with other open source projects (e.g. *icepyx*), and combine development efforts when appropriate. It has also allowed data scientists to use individual components of our system that they deploy themselves without using the entire SlideRule system. For example, the components of SlideRule that read HDF5 data directly from the Cloud are also used by seismologists working with time series data.

Complementing these goals, the code repositories for SlideRule are structured in a way to maximize the reusability of the code. The SlideRule project consists of four distinct sets of code repositories. The **core framework** repository which is mission agnostic and provides the base functionality of SlideRule, the **client library** repositories which contain client language specific code (e.g. Python, R), the **mission extension** repositories which contain all the code for each mission a SlideRule deployment supports, and the **infrastructure** repository which contains the scripts and definition files for deploying the SlideRule system. By separating out the repositories in this way, potential collaborators and users can focus on the part of the system most pertinent to them without being overwhelmed by components they don't need. For instance, an institution wishing to rehost a SlideRule deployment on premise for ICESat-2 data could fork our core framework, mission plugin, and client repositories, and provide their own infrastructure.

Extensive Documentation

SlideRule is extensively documented so that beginners and experts have a well-organized set of reference materials. We also provide example Jupyter notebooks that users can start from when building their own data analysis scripts. Documentation is provided via the Read the Docs open source framework for generating documentation, and is hosted alongside a static website generated via Jekyll that contains various howtos, release notes, and overviews of different aspects of the SlideRule system.

Reproducibility through Version Control

The full stack of Cloud infrastructure, tagged images, and versioned client source code, can be redeployed in order to reproduce historical results. Configuration management is achieved by strict version control of three aspects of the SlideRule system: source code, Docker images, and Amazon Machine Images (AMIs). Each deployment of SlideRule originates from a tagged release of the source code. The released source code is then used to generate and tag the Docker images and AMIs used by the deployment. SlideRule provides both a client API and a server API for retrieving the version of the code, containers, and machine images that are running. User scripts and notebooks use these APIs to uniquely identify the version and configuration of the system fulfilling their processing requests.

² <https://github.com/ICESat2-SlideRule>

3. Component Technologies

Two transformative capabilities of new science data processing systems, modeled by SlideRule, are: providing higher-level data products through on demand services as opposed to pre-generated archives available for download, and the development and use of cloud-native data access libraries.

Service-Based Data Distribution

The University of Washington's deployment of SlideRule provides web services that return global gridded elevations generated from ICESat-2's level 2 photon cloud data. It does this using a customized version of a ground finding algorithm developed for one of ICESat-2's level 3 data products. By providing the results of this ground algorithm as a service instead of a pre-generated product, the following benefits are realized:

- ***Processing options are made available to the user.*** In SlideRule the user can specify multiple processing parameters, including selecting between multiple photon classification algorithms, some of which use external datasets; whereas in the official product, the algorithm is hardcoded.
- ***Processing parameters are customizable and can be explored.*** In SlideRule, generating an elevation product over snow-covered mountainous areas benefit from using a smaller length scale than the one chosen for all of the current level 3 elevation products produced by the ICESat-2 mission.
- ***New algorithms, improvements, and fixes are immediately available.*** In SlideRule, when a user finds an issue or requests a feature, we can immediately make the change available to the user. We are not constrained by product release cycles, reprocessing large backlogs of historical data, and the time it takes to upload and download new datasets. All results are generated on demand and therefore immediately include all fixes and features currently in the code.
- ***Services build on each other.*** When institutions move to a service-based model for data distribution, those services can be integrated with other systems such as situational awareness and warning systems, and geographic information systems.

Cloud-Native Data Access

The ICESat-2 datasets, generated and stored in AWS S3 by NASA, are in the HDF5 format, which was originally developed for file-based high performance computing systems. The HDF5 format, along with NetCDF (which uses HDF5 underneath) is used for a large portion of NASA's Earth Science archives. Yet the existing tooling around HDF5 is not well suited for working with files in S3, and current approaches to solve this problem have a common weakness in requiring either the transformation of the data into a different format or the creation of supplemental meta-datasets that index the original data.

While we are strong proponents of institutions adopting newer, more cloud-friendly, data formats for their science archives, as developers of SlideRule, we did not want to require users of our system to run transformation pipelines and maintain supplemental data repositories. As a result, we developed a **cloud-optimized read-only library for HDF5 (*H5Coro*)**³, which was written from scratch in C++ and targets high-throughput / high-latency environments such as cloud-based object stores. *H5Coro* *performantly reads HDF5 files in place without the need for supplemental indexes, and reduced the cost of running SlideRule by two orders of magnitude.*

³ https://www.hdfgroup.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/JPSwinski_H5Coro.pdf

4. Downstream Interoperability

SlideRule implements different data processing functions that support downstream data consumers: source dataset filtering and subsetting, customizable data transformation, the use of open standards, and open-source integrations.

Filtering and Subsetting

The initial step of a data processing request is subsetting and filtering the source datasets based on temporal, spatial, and metadata constraints. SlideRule relies heavily upon NASA's Common Metadata Repository (CMR) system and we strongly believe that institutions that produce and host science data must also invest in metadata services alongside their data. NASA's CMR system is limited in the size and complexity of the queries it supports, in which cases, SlideRule provides features to work around those limitations. Specifically, geographic features that require large sets of vertices to define, and include many distinct shapes, cannot be processed by the CMR system. Unfortunately, such characteristics are common for glacier and sea ice features studied by the ICESat-2 community. Approaches to mitigate these limitations are under active development by the SlideRule team.

Customized Transformations

SlideRule's services lower the barrier of access to ICESat-2's datasets by offloading the complexity and fixed costs associated with processing ICESat-2's raw photon cloud, and providing gridded elevations customized by the data user for their science investigation. As a concrete example of the need for these types of transformations, consider that the original NASA ICESat mission, which launched in 2003, produced 148GB of global elevation data. That data could be downloaded at 6MBps in just under 1 day, stored on a single harddrive on a single workstation, and directly analyzed forever after. ICESat-2 (the follow-on mission), launched in 2018 and has produced 320TB of data with 100TB of data being added each year. In order to download the existing dataset at 100MBps, it would take 296 days, and require 40 workstations with 8TBs of storage each to hold.

Open standards

Future ESO architecture should embrace emerging standards in data and metadata formats for Cloud-hosted data. As already discussed, SlideRule depends on NASA CMR, which accelerates extension to missions other than ICESat-2 because there is a standard set of queries to build upon. Emerging metadata formats specifically focused on Cloud-hosted archives, such as SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogs (STAC) should be considered for even more interoperability going forward.

Open-source integrations

Analysts of data products increasingly expect the ability to stream datasets into their programming language of choice. While the SlideRule processing architecture is agnostic to client-side programming languages, client libraries can implement conveniences to return in-memory human-friendly objects rather than machine-friendly JSON or binary files. For example, SlideRule's Python client returns tabular results as GeoPandas GeoDataFrames (GeoPandas being the leading open-source Python library for geospatial vector data); and since SlideRule is coordinated through HTTP requests, similar paradigms in other open source programming languages such as R and Julia are straightforward.

5. Other Recommendations

We recommend that future mission science data processing systems support not just distributing higher-level data products as a service, but also running user provided science data processing algorithms as a service.

Bring Your Own Algorithm

One of the ultimate goals for SlideRule is to support researchers executing their own algorithms without having to worry about any of the infrastructure needed to scale compute resources and access large archives. The current roadmap for SlideRule supporting the execution of user provided algorithms has three paths: script execution, container execution, and machine learning model execution.

Executing user provided scripts can be achieved by sandboxing a Lua interpreter (i.e. protecting the O.S. from the execution of the script). Currently, each REST API call to SlideRule instantiates a self-contained Lua environment and executes a Lua script corresponding to the endpoint accessed. These scripts are trusted components of the SlideRule framework and mission plugins; but in the future, we hope to open up the architecture to allow users to provide their own Lua scripts at the time of the request. This will give users fine-grained control over how data is accessed and processed, using a scripting language that is both performant and easy to learn.

Executing user provided containers can be achieved by sandboxing the EC2 instances running those containers (i.e. protecting the AWS account from the actions of the container). Currently, the SlideRule Provisioning System provisions compute-resources based on pre-negotiated allocations of funding and runs Docker containers developed by the SlideRule team on those resources. In the future, users could provide their own Docker containers that adhere to a set of SlideRule interface requirements, and we could run those containers using our provisioning and cost allocation system.

Executing user provided and pre-trained machine learning models can be achieved by standardizing mission dataset inputs, and running the TensorFlow Lite framework within SlideRule as one of its plugins. In the future, users would then be able to provide pre-trained models at the time of the processing request, and have SlideRule respond with subsets of the data that match the features detected by the model.

Community training and networking

Cloud technologies are evolving extremely rapidly, as is software used to analyze Cloud-hosted datasets. Furthermore, many commercial remote sensing companies and other space agencies are constantly innovating improved processing system architectures. What is optimal now, will likely cease to be so on a 5-10 year horizon. Therefore, it is important to continue to engage with the broader community all the way from data producers to data consumers to stay current with emerging technologies. Already, the Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) organize valuable annual meetings for networking and exchange of ideas. Furthermore, a move to open-source on-demand services blurs the line of a historically clear division between data producers and data consumers. As more scientific users are able to create large derived datasets and participate in software development, there should be regular training on effective use of Cloud resources and open source software development for scientific data consumers.

References

JP Swinski, Tyler Sutterley, David Shean, & Scott Henderson. (2021). ICESat2-SlideRule/sliderule: 1.3.2 (1.3.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5799545>

Scheick, J. et al., (2019). icepyx: Python tools for obtaining and working with ICESat-2 data. <https://github.com/icesat2py/icepyx>.